

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 10.4: UPDATED STAKEHOLDER DATABASE MADE AVAILABLE ON THE INTERNAL PLATFORM

Public summary of
confidential report

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Work Package / Task:

10 / T10.1 Establish and maintain
multi- actor interactive
communication platforms

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Summary:

This deliverable provides an overview and status of the stakeholder database developed in SeaMark. The database is available to the SeaMark project partners in order to facilitate efficient interaction and allow for continuous exploration of cross-collaboration stakeholder networks.

The methodology applied comprised an online form (i.e. survey) that was shared with project partners in order to provide input on key stakeholders for communication, dissemination and exploitation of the 12 SeaMark products and other key exploitable results. 110 stakeholders were identified, and the results were aggregated into an Excel form and segmented according to the “influence vs. interest grid” described in the SeaMark communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (CDEP). This includes:

- High level and key stakeholders (high influence, high interest)
- Mid-level stakeholders or facilitators at risk (high influence, low interest)
- Multipliers and target groups (low influence, high interest)
- Potentially interested partners (low influence, low interest)

Examples of the applications and use-cases of the stakeholder list were identified and described.

The deliverable serves as a baseline for project related CDE activities (e.g. organisation of workshops), to be continually updated throughout the project period in order to maximise impacts.

The online form will be taken offline at the end of the project. The deliverable will be stored on a secure, trusted repository for the required length of time post-project as stipulated in the Grant Agreement. SUBMARINER is the owner of the stakeholder list and sensitive information (personal data) will be deleted from SUBMARINER’s servers after its intended use.

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